

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Complexes of Cobalt Hexathiocyanates of Tin (IV) and Titanium (IV)

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$K_2Sn(NCS)_6$, $CoSn(NCS)_6$ and $CoM(NCS)_6XL$ ($M = Sn(IV)$, $Ti(IV)$, $L =$ pyridine(py), 3-cyanopyridine(cpy), isonicotinic acid hydrazide(inh), nicotinamide(nia), ethylnicotinate(ent) and ethylenediamine(en) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectral studies. These studies indicate the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate in $K_2Sn(NCS)_6$, and bridged dithiocyanate in $CoM(NCS)_6$. $CoM(NCS)_6XL$ have cationic anionic structure $[CoL_x][Sn(NCS)_6]$ ($X = 4$ or 6) in which L is bonded to cobalt and thiocyanate to tin(IV) or titanium(IV), through nitrogen.

THIOCYANATE ion has three modes of bonding, through nitrogen(-NCS), through sulphur (-SCN) and as bridging(-NCS-)¹. These bonding modes depend upon (a) hard and soft nature of the metal², (b) the nature of the ligand³. This criterion has been extensively investigated in simple thiocyanate complexes^{3,4}. Very recently, Rivest *et al.*^{5,6,7} have studied the effect of change of metal and ligand on the mode of thiocyanate bonding in a number of tetrathiocyanate complexes.

These effects on hexathiocyanate complexes have never been studied. The known hexathiocyanates can be divided into two groups—one in which the metals are in oxidation state +2 or +3, and the other in which the oxidation state is +4 or +5. The hexathiocyanates of the former type are quite a few, but that of latter type are only few and to the authors' knowledge only seven references are known. Since we shall confine ourselves to the hexathiocyanate of the metals in higher oxidation state, we are reporting all such known compounds and their study.

Tramer⁸ first reported the metal hexathiocyanates of Pt(IV) and synthesised $M Pt(SCN)_6$ ($M = Co$, Pb , Hg , Zn , Cu and Fe). He suggested a bridging structure to these complexes. Schmitz *et al.*⁹ and Bailey^{10,11} reported hexathiocyanates of the type $K_2M(NCS)_6$ ($M = Ti(IV)$, $Zr(IV)$, $Hf(IV)$, $Re(V)$ and $Pt(IV)$) and have only given their infrared assignments. Knox and Brown¹² *et al.* and Zenker¹³ *et al.* have synthesised sodium and potassium salts of Nb(V) and Ta(V) hexathiocyanates. Brown has studied their infrared spectra in detail. Potassium has been replaced by quaternary ions¹¹⁻¹⁴ to see the effect of this change on the structure of the complexes.

There is no reference available for $Sn(NCS)_6^{2-}$ ion, though analogous hexacyanate $(Me_4N)_2Sn(NCO)_6$ has been reported by Forster and Goodgame¹⁵.

In this communication the synthesis and structural discussion of potassium and cobalt hexathio-

cyanates of tin(IV) and titanium(IV) are presented. Since maximum covalency of cobalt and tin or titanium is not achieved in $CoM(NCS)_6$, there exists a unique interest of reacting these thiocyanates with Lewis bases. This interest has never been explored. We have reacted $CoM(NCS)_6$ with certain pyridine derivatives and ethylenediamine and have prepared complexes. The structure of these complexes and the mode of thiocyanate bonding have been discussed also.

Experimental

Materials and manipulations: Tin(IV) and titanium(IV) chlorides were purified by the method of Hildebrand and Caster¹⁶. Reagent grade anhydrous cobalt(II) chloride (Alfa Inorganics) and potassium thiocyanate (B.D.H.) were used after drying in vacuum for 24 hr. Ethylenediamine(en), pyridine(py) B.D.H. and isonicotinic acid hydrazide(inh) (Aldrich Chemicals) were recrystallised from alcohol and dried in vacuum. Ethyl-nicotinate(ent) and 3-cyanopyridine(3cpy) were synthesised by standard methods¹⁷ from nicotinic acid and nicotinamide (B.D.H.) respectively, which were purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Ethanol, acetone, ether and hexane (B.D.H.) were purified and dried by known methods.

Preparation of complexes:

Preparation of $K_2Sn(NCS)_6$: 2 m.mol. of tin(IV) chloride and 12 m.mol. of potassium thiocyanate were separately dissolved in acetonitrile. The two solutions were mixed and stirred for 6 hr and filtered. The residue (KCl) was rejected and the filtrate was concentrated by vacuum evaporation and placed in vacuum desiccator. White crystalline mass separated out. The solvent was removed by decantation and compound dried in vacuum. Whole procedure was carried under strict dry conditions in a dry box, flushed with nitrogen.

Preparation of CoSn(NCS)₆: This complex was prepared by two methods:

(i) To an acetonitrile solution of K₂Sn(NCS)₆ calculated amount of anhydrous cobalt(II) chloride was added and stirred. After 6 hr, precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off and from the filtrate bluish green crystals were crystallised.

(ii) To a 5 m.mol. solution of stannic chloride in dry ethanol, 5 m.mol. of anhydrous cobalt(II) chloride and 30 m.mol. of potassium thiocyanate were added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 12 hr at room temperature and then filtered. The residue was rejected and the filtrate concentrated by vacuum evaporation. On addition of dry ether, a bluish green solid separated, which was washed with ether and dried in vacuum.

CoTi(NCS)₆ was similarly prepared.

Preparation of CoSn(NCS)₆XL (X = 4 or 6; L = py, nia, 3-cpy, ent, inh and en): Two solutions of CoSn(NCS)₆ (1.5 m.mol.) in alcohol were prepared in two different flasks A and B. To flask A 6 m.mol. of ligands and to flask B 9 m.mol. of ligands were added. The reaction mixture in both the flasks were stirred for 6 hr. In flask A blue green complexes and in flask B pink complexes were formed, which were filtered, washed with solvent and dried in vacuum. In case of ethylnicotinate, the complex remained dissolved in the solvent and could be separated only after concentration in vacuum and subsequent addition of dry ether.

Complexes of CoTi(NCS)₆ were similarly prepared.

Analysis: Thiocyanate was estimated by Volhards method, tin and titanium as oxides, sulphur as

sulphate and cobalt as anthranilate, in the filtrate from which tin or titanium was removed. Analytical results are included in Table 1.

Physical measurements: The infrared spectra of ligands, metal hexathiocyanates and their complexes were recorded on a Perkin Elmer model 621 or 457 spectrophotometer in the range 4000–200 cm⁻¹. Samples were run as nujol mulls using CsI plates. Spectra of soluble ligands were also recorded in solutions. Electronic spectra were obtained on a Cary-14 spectrophotometer between 1700–300 nm. Samples were run as their methanol, ethanol, or acetone solutions depending on the solubility of the compound.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature by Guoy's method using CoHg(SCN)₄ as standard¹⁸. The diamagnetic corrections were made by the method outlined by Figgis and Lewis¹⁹.

Molar conductance of the compounds was determined in alcohol with the help of conductivity bridge model Philips PR 9500. Molar conductance data are included in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Results of our investigation have been divided into three groups:

I. *K₂Sn(NCS)₆*: A metal thiocyanate has three modes of fundamental vibrations, viz., C–N stretching (γ_1), C–S stretching (γ_2) and NCS bending (γ_3). The positions of these bands are in the region 2000–2180 cm⁻¹, 650–860 cm⁻¹ and 400–500 cm⁻¹ respectively. In addition to these bands overtones (2 δ NCS) in the region 800–1000 cm⁻¹ and metal-NCS bands in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA

Compounds	colour	M.P. °C	% Co		% Sn or Ti		% NCS		% sulphur		Molar M/512	conduc- tance M/1024 [λ mo, cm ² mol ⁻¹]
			obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.	obs.	cal.		
K ₂ Sn(NCS) ₆	white	—	—	—	21.25	21.78	62.97	63.85	35.76	35.23	145.70	157.73
CoSn(NCS) ₆	blue	178(d)	10.92	11.22	21.81	22.40	62.05	64.43	34.94	36.28	23.40	27.31
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 4py	green	150	6.75	7.09	13.65	14.00	40.80	40.13	22.85	23.00	98.50	102.60
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 4ent	greenish blue	190	5.42	5.19	11.24	10.78	31.03	30.60	17.01	16.90	75.75	98.04
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 4nia	bluish green	120	5.40	5.83	11.93	11.65	34.10	34.35	17.49	18.00	78.50	106.40
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 6nia	light pink	105(d)	4.38	4.69	9.75	9.38	28.00	27.68	12.58	12.80	81.50	102.00
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 6cpy	pink	140(d)	4.89	5.13	10.30	10.27	29.80	30.28	15.97	16.71	58.50	78.45
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 6inh	pink	165(d)	4.54	4.25	9.13	8.50	24.95	25.10	14.20	13.95	58.70	80.35
CoSn(NCS) ₆ 3en	brown	158(d)	7.95	8.30	16.56	16.76	49.70	48.92	26.97	27.22	85.50	110.60
CoTi(NCS) ₆	green	200(d)	13.45	12.96	10.30	10.52	74.80	76.48	41.50	42.17	27.01	29.87
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 4py	green	190(d)	8.01	7.76	6.50	6.23	44.77	45.14	24.48	24.89	87.90	103.23
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 4ent	green	190	5.80	5.51	4.55	4.86	32.01	32.86	18.00	18.15	78.75	100.04
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 4nia	green	140	6.65	6.25	5.34	5.09	35.89	36.90	21.97	20.96	97.80	110.60
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 6nia	pink	125(d)	5.14	4.97	4.35	4.04	30.10	29.31	17.01	16.37	91.50	112.70
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 6cpy	light pink	168(d)	5.80	5.46	4.20	4.47	32.00	32.35	17.80	17.68	76.50	90.60
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 6inh	pink	155(d)	4.80	4.59	4.02	3.76	28.30	27.25	14.90	15.03	68.70	98.20
CoTi(NCS) ₆ 3en	brownish pink	210(d)	9.05	8.40	7.40	7.56	52.98	54.80	29.18	30.02	56.32	83.36

(d) = decomposes.

the region 200–400 cm^{-1} are also observed. The positions and the nature of these bands indicate the nature of thiocyanate bonding. The positions of γ_1 and γ_2 are useful for determining the site of thiocyanate bonding, whereas the number of these bands is useful for determining the configuration of the complexes, for instance cis octahedral has two C–N bands while trans has only one²⁰. Knox and Brown¹² have shown the presence of six bands in C–N region for hexathiocyanate of Oh symmetry e.g. $\text{KM}(\text{NCS})_6$ and $\text{K}_2\text{M}(\text{NCS})_6$, where $\text{M} = \text{Nb}(\text{IV and V})$ and $\text{Ta}(\text{V})$. They have also shown that the number of C–N bands becomes three or four, when potassium is replaced by quaternary ion. This effect of change of cation on the number of bands has not been discussed. It is, perhaps, due to some structural change, which they have not pointed out. It is also evident from other work¹⁰ that the quaternary ions cause decrease in number of C–N bands. In tetrathiocyanate ions of the type $\text{M}(\text{NCS})_4^{-2}$, the number of bands is generally two when the cation is potassium and one when it is quaternary ion^{8,10,11,12}. The

position of C–N in N-bonded hexathiocyanates is in the range 1910–2095 cm^{-1} , whereas the corresponding range in tetrathiocyanates is narrow (2040–2080 cm^{-1}).

In respect of C–S bands the number is three when the corresponding number of C–N is six, and one or two when the number of C–N is three or four. In tetrathiocyanates this number is generally one. The position of these bands is in the range of 820–940 cm^{-1} for N-bonded hexathiocyanates which is much higher as compared to N-bonded dithiocyanates or tetrathiocyanates e.g. (780–860 cm^{-1}).

The number of bands due to NCS bending in hexathiocyanates and tetrathiocyanates is almost the same and no distinction can be made on the basis of number of bands in this region. The range, however, is useful. In case of N-bonded hexathiocyanate, the range is 420–510 cm^{-1} and for tetrathiocyanate, it is 450–490 cm^{-1} .

The M–NCS band is very useful for the purpose of pointing out the nature of bonding and the configura-

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BAND ASSIGNMENTS (cm^{-1})

Complexes	C–N stretching frequency (ν_1)	C–S stretching frequency (ν_2)	NCS bending frequency (ν_3)	Co–SCN	M–NCS	Co–L
$\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_6^a$	1940–2100svbr	873m, 860sh, 740m, 720m;	510m, 483s, 470s;	—	310vs 230ms	—
$\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_6^b$	2100sh, 2040s, 2026s, 2010ms, 1940sh, 1960m;	875m, 860sh, 740sh, 725sh;	511m, 485s, 472s;	—	310vs 250m	—
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_6$	2160s, 2070sh, 2080sh;	780m, 745sh, 730s;	485w, 465s, 420w;	285m 265sh	310s	—
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_6$	2155s, 2105sh, 2070sh;	780m, 740sh, 724m;	485w, 460s, 426sh;	280m 262sh	307s	—
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_64\text{py}$	2050sb, 2005sh;	815m, 770w;	485sh, 470m;	—	300s	270m
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_64\text{ent}$	2050sb, 2000sh;	830sh, 815w;	480sh, 465m;	—	303s	270m
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_64\text{nia}$	2055sb, 1997sh;	840m, 815sh;	485s, 460sh;	—	315sb	230m
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_66\text{nia}$	2050sb;	830sh, 790m;	485m, 460sh;	—	310s 290w	280sh 250w
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_66\text{cpy}$	2050sb, 2040sh;	820s, 790m;	487s, 478m;	—	290s	235m
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_66\text{inh}$	2070sb, 1045sh;	840m, 750m, 765sh;	— 470m;	—	330sh 285mb	250m
$\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_63\text{en}$	2040sh; 2010s;	860w, 840sh, 770w;	485sh, 470m;	—	310sh 285m	250w
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_64\text{py}$	2055sb, 2025sh;	840wb, 750m;	480mb, 460sh;	—	310w	250mb
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_64\text{ent}$	2050sb;	830w, 790sh;	480w, 460sh;	—	320m	245w
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_64\text{nia}$	2080sb, 2015sh;	820sh, 815s, 750m;	488sh, 470s;	—	300s	240wb
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_66\text{nia}$	2070sb;	825w, 780m;	488sh; 470sh;	—	315s	250m
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_66\text{cpy}$	2070sb, 2010sh;	820s, 790s;	485s, 475s;	—	295s	250m
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_66\text{inh}$	2065sb;	830w, 793m;	480m —	—	320m	260mb
$\text{CoTi}(\text{NCS})_63\text{en}$	2080sb, 2050sh;	865w, 780w;	475m —	—	320m	245m

s = strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder, w = weak, br = broad;

^a = spectra of the sample using concentrated nujol emulsion;

^b = spectra of the sample using very much diluted nujol emulsion.

tion of the complexes. In a hexathiocyanate ion one strong band has been observed, the position of which has been shown dependent upon the oxidation state of the metal. For instance, the position of this band in trivalent salts lies above those for bivalent salts²¹. This value goes higher to 355 cm⁻¹ in pentavalent niobium. This strong band has been shown by Goodgame²² to be due to triply degenerate (T_{1u}) M-N stretch of $M(NCS)_6^{-x}$ ion which has Oh symmetry. When Oh symmetry of this ion is disturbed the band is either broadened or splits into three bands of medium intensity.

In our complex $K_2M(NCS)_6$, we observe one broad and intense band for C-N stretching frequency. The range of broadness is 1940-2100 cm⁻¹. This broadness of the band is unusual and appears to be a mixture of number of bands. This band is resolved into six weak bands, when nujol emulsion of the sample is very much diluted. This is in conformity with the work of Bohland¹³ who observed one strong broad band at about 1978 cm⁻¹ for $NaNb(NCS)_6$. In the similar compound $KNb(NCS)_6$, this broad band is resolved into six bands ranging from 1910-2080 cm⁻¹. Similarly Brown and Knox¹² noticed the presence of one strong band in this region. Spectrum of $Sn(NCS)_6^{-2}$ ion is quite similar to that of pentavalent niobium hexathiocyanate ion $Nb(NCS)_6^{-2}$. This resemblance is perhaps due to similar electronic configuration.

The C-S region shows the presence of four bands in the range 720-860 cm⁻¹. The number and position of these bands are consistent with N-bonded hexathiocyanate ion^{10,13,23}. We have earlier pointed out that the number of C-S bands is four when the number of C-N bands is six. The presence of four C-S bands in our complex also indirectly suggests

that the broad C-N band is a mixture of six bands. The bands at 970 cm⁻¹ and 930 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to overtones (2δ NCS).

The number and position of NCS bands are also very much typical of N-bonded hexathiocyanates^{10,11}.

Sn-NCS stretching band appears at 316 cm⁻¹, the position of which is consistent with oxidation state of the metal. There is another band of medium intensity at 230 cm⁻¹ which we assign to N-Sn-N deformation mode.

II. $CoM(NCS)_6$ [$M = Sn(IV), Ti(IV)$]: When potassium of $K_2Sn(NCS)_6$ is replaced by Co(II), following changes in spectral bands are observed. The number of C-N bands decreases to three, their position changes to (2070-2160 cm⁻¹) and the peaks get well defined. Similarly the position of C-S bands is shifted to 720-780 cm⁻¹ and their number decreases to three. The position of NCS band changes to 420-485 cm⁻¹. The position, nature and the number of these bands very clearly suggest that both, bridging and terminal thiocyanate groups are present. As compared to $CoM(NCS)_4$ ($M = Zn, Cd, \text{ and } Hg$) the number of bands in C-N, C-S and NCS is more in $CoSn(NCS)_6$ which is due to the presence of terminal thiocyanate in the latter and absence of the same in the former. Thus $CoHg(SCN)_4$ appears to be polymeric (Fig. 3) and $CoSn(NCS)_6$ monomeric (Fig. 1).

Tramer⁸ has also reported the infrared spectra of $M Pt(SCN)_6$ ($M = Fe, Co, Cu, Zn, Cd \text{ and } Hg$), in which he, too, has observed the presence of bridging thiocyanates. In these complexes the sulphur end of thiocyanate is linked with platinum(IV), and nitrogen to M(II) (Fig. 2). In our complexes the

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BAND ASSIGNMENTS, SPECTRAL PARAMETERS AND BOHR MAGNETON VALUES OF Co(II) TETRAHEDRAL AND OCTAHEDRAL COMPLEXES (35000-5000 cm⁻¹)

Complexes	Spectral band positions	assignments					
		ν_3	ν_2	10Dq	B'	β	B.M. μ_{eff}
$CoSn(NCS)_6$	17200, 16129, 720, 6500;	16129	7230	4200	717	.73	4.5
$CoTi(NCS)_6$	17245, 16130, 8330, 7200, 6452;	16130	7200	4180	719	.74	4.5
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 4py$	17450, 16290, 8182, 7225, 6452;	16290	7225	4145	729	.75	4.4
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 4nia$	18000, 16000, 7190, 6430;	16000	7190	4177	723	.74	4.6
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 4ent$	17500, 16150, 7200, 6225;	16150	7200	4180	720	.74	4.7
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 6nia$	23200, 19230, 15750, 7235, 6430;	19230	15750	8412	865	.89	5.2
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 6cpy$	21277, 19230, 15700, 7230, 6452;	19230	15700	8390	867	.89	5.3
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 6inh$	23200, 19450, 15400, 7248, 6500;	19420	15400	8236	889	.91	5.2
$CoSn(NCS)_6 \cdot 3en$	22220, 19270, 16000, 7118, 6430;	19270	16000	8540	860	.89	4.9
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 4py$	17241, 16180, 8285, 7142, 6474;	16180	7142	4142	726	.75	4.5
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 4nia$	17950, 16130, 8200, 7160, 6445;	16130	7160	4155	722	.74	4.6
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 4ent$	17430, 16137, 7180, 6270;	16137	7180	4168	721	.74	4.7
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 6nia$	22370, 19350, 15650, 7300, 6540;	19350	15650	8360	875	.90	5.4
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 6cpy$	21053, 19231, 15500, 7246, 6730;	19231	15500	8340	883	.91	5.2
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 6inh$	22250, 19500, 15350, 7270, 6645;	19500	15350	8215	896	.923	5.4
$CoTi(NCS)_6 \cdot 3en$	22220, 19350, 15900, 7118, 6430, 5900;	19350	15900	8489	868	.89	4.9

nitrogen end of thiocyanate will be bonded to tin(IV) and sulphur to cobalt(II), according to H.S.A.B. theory²⁴.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3. $(\text{CoHg}(\text{SCN})_4)$

III. $\text{CoM}(\text{NCS})_6\text{XL}$ (L = py, 3-cpy, nia, ent. inh and en) :

The structure of $\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_6$ as presented in preceding discussion clearly shows that the maximum covalency of six in Co(II) and Sn(IV) is not achieved and this complex has the possibility of acting as Lewis acid. On reaction with certain pyridine derivatives and ethylenediamine it accordingly forms complexes. The infrared spectra of these complexes show following deviations from the spectra of $\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_6$ and $\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_6$. (Table 4).

TABLE 4

	$\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_6$	$\text{CoM}(\text{NCS})_6$	$\text{CoM}(\text{NCS})_6\text{XL}$
CN stretching	1940—2100 cm ⁻¹ (very broad)	2070—2160 cm ⁻¹ (3-bands)	1995—2080 cm ⁻¹ (1-sbr, 2-sh)
CS "	720—880 (4-bands)	725—780 (3-bands)	785—850 (2-3 bands)
NCS deform.	470—510 (3-bands)	425—485 (3-bands)	450—485 (2-bands)
M-NCS stretch.	310 (s) (1-band)	270—315 (3-bands)	300—325 (1-band)
Co-L "	—	—	240—280 (1-band)

The position of C-N, C-S and NCS very clearly show that only nitrogen bonded thiocyanate is present in these complexes, which is either attached to M(IV) ion or to Co(II) ion. Since the former is a hard acid and the latter is comparatively soft, thiocyanate will prefer Sn(IV) for coordination. The band at 310 cm⁻¹, which is triply degenerate does not split, showing very clearly that Oh symmetry

of $\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_6^{-2}$ is maintained. If this is true the ligands have to be linked to cobalt in the following manner :

The molar conductance of this series of complexes in alcohol (70–160 ohm⁻¹ cm² per mol.) also shows that the complexes are ionic. Hence the above structure appears to be possible. All the ligands (pyridine derivatives and ethylenediamine) when added to $\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_6$ in slight excess the colour changes from blue green to pink, which clearly shows that ligands link to cobalt and not to tin. This also appears reasonable because the thiocyanate bridge in between cobalt and tin in $\text{CoSn}(\text{NCS})_6$ is weakly bonded to cobalt through sulphur as compared to tin through nitrogen.

Very recently Co-L (L = py. derivatives) has been assigned at 250–290 cm⁻¹ in a number of complexes^{6,7}. A band at 250–265 cm⁻¹ is present in our complexes which likewise can be assigned to Co-N(L). The presence of this band also supports that ligands are coordinated to cobalt.

Since the complexes are cationic and anionic, their spectra should be identical to $\text{K}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})_6$, but a reference to Table 4 shows a number of deviations. These deviations are due to some cationic effects, because the cation in these complexes is changed from a smaller potassium ion to bigger $[\text{CoL}_x]^{-2}$ ion. The effect of cation on the spectral and position of thiocyanate has never been discussed but has been observed in many cases. Brown¹², Bohland^{13,23} and Bailey¹⁰ have also observed a decrease in number of C-N and C-S bands, when potassium of $\text{KM}(\text{NCS})_6$ (M = Nb, Ta) and $\text{K}_2\text{M}(\text{NCS})_6$ (M = Zr, Hf), is replaced by bigger ions like tetraethyl ammonium, tetrabutyl ammonium and tetraphenyl arsonium ions.

All pyridine derivatives show features of coordination through pyridyl nitrogen except isonicotinic acid hydrazide, where coordination takes place through carbonyl oxygen.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectral bands, the assignments and the parameters derived from them are represented in Table 3. All spectral measurements have been recorded in acetone, methanol or ethanol solutions. To see the effect of solvolysis we have also recorded spectra as nujol mulls, by the technique of Lee²⁵. Since there were no differences in the position of bands in solution and solid phase spectra, we have used the solution spectral bands, for various calculations, as they were better resolved.

All blue or green complexes $\text{CoM}(\text{NCS})_6$ and $\text{CoM}(\text{NCS})_6\text{XL}$ show absorption bands in the range 7000–7300 cm⁻¹ and 16000–16300 cm⁻¹. The former can be assigned by γ_2 arising from transition ${}^4A_2 - {}^4T_1(\text{P})$ and the latter to γ_3 arising from the transition ${}^4A_2 - {}^4T_{1g}(\text{F})$. The molar absorptivity, position of these bands, magnetic moment values and colour of the complexes very clearly show that they

are tetrahedral in configuration. We have therefore used secular equation of Tanabe and Sugano²⁶, for tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes for the purpose of deriving Dq and B' parameters. The Dq values of CoM(NCS)₆ are lower as compared to CoHg(SCN)₄, which is due to the change of bonding site in two complexes. In the latter case cobalt is bound to nitrogen and in the former to sulphur.

The red or brown complexes have absorption peaks in the region 18000–19500 cm⁻¹ and at about 15500 cm⁻¹. These bands are assigned to the transitions (γ_3) ⁴T_{1g}—⁴T_{1g}(P) and (γ_2) ⁴A_{2g}—⁴T_{1g} respectively. The colour, magnetic moment and the values of Dq, B' of these complexes are in the range of octahedral cobalt(II) complexes²⁷.

Main observations :

1. In a complex of the type CoM(NCS)₆ (M = Ti(IV), Zr(IV) and Hf(IV), Sn(IV) cobalt is linked to sulphur end of thiocyanate and M to nitrogen end.

2. Metals in higher oxidation state cause decrease in C–N stretching frequency range and increase in C–S stretching frequency, and generally prefer nitrogen end of thiocyanate.

3. The number of thiocyanate bands in C–N and C–S region decreases when potassium of K₂Sn(NCS)₆ is replaced by [CoL_x]⁺² ion.

4. The thiocyanate bridge in CoSn(NCS)₆ is weak because it breaks on reaction with ligands.

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